

Editorial

Antifungal drug resistance mechanism in clinical and environmental *Aspergillus* species

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Aspergillus fungi are the most common mold with several species. *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Aspergillus flavus* are the most common species to produce toxins that affect humans, animals and plants health, leading to immunosuppression and carcinogenicity. Aspergillosis is the most dangerous cause of morbidity and mortality in patients and severity of the disease depends on the involvement of *Aspergillus* fungal exposure (1). Azole antifungal agents help to control the disease caused by *Aspergillus* spp. However, these fungus becoming resistance to azole compounds. *A. fumigatus* is not a phytopathogen. However, it is the most common cause of aspergillosis in the United States and Europe. Several agricultural fungicides deployed against plant pathogenic molds such as *Fusarium*, *Mycosphaerella*, and *A. flavus* also show activity against *A. fumigatus* in the environment and exposure of non-target fungi is inevita-

ble (2). Here, we aim to report the underlying resistance mechanism in the progress of azole resistance and highlight the therapeutic options.

Previously several azole-based antimycotic drugs have been developed, among which itraconazole (ITZ), voriconazole (VRZ), posaconazole (PSZ), and (lately) isavuconazole (ISAZ) are mainly used for the treatment of aspergilloses. Azoles are steric inhibitors of sterol 14 α - demethylase enzymes catalyzing a critical step in ergosterol biosynthesis (3). Therefore, azole resistance in *Aspergillus* spp. have been a matter of serious clinical concern. Different patterns of resistance are seen, with multi azole and pan-azole resistance being more common than resistance to a single triazole. A variety of mutations occur in the coding region of *cyp51A*, a gene encoding a sterol 14 α -demethylase in *A. fumigatus*. Today, the most frequently observed resistance allele consists of a 34-bp tandem repeat in

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the promoter region of *cyp51A* combined with the L98H substitution (TR34/L98H). This allele confers high ITZ resistance and various levels of cross-resistance to other azoles. Together with strains carrying a TR46 allele in conjunction with Y121F and T289A exchanges, such strains are thought to spread globally through the environment (4,5), potentially propagated using 14 α -demethylase inhibitor (DMI) fungicides in agriculture. In fact, for many plant-pathogenic fungi, similar resistance mechanisms toward agricultural azole-based fungicides are observed (6). Resistant *Aspergillus* strains present in the environment are thought to exogenously colonize or infect susceptible hosts. These observations are of significant concern, as an exclusion of azole-based antifungals from prophylaxis or first-line treatment of invasive aspergillosis dramatically limits treatment options (7).

Meis et al (8) clinical studies have shown that two-thirds of patients with azole-resistant infections had no previous history of azole therapy and high mortality rates between 50% and 100% are reported in azole-resistant invasive aspergillosis. The resistance phenotype is associated with key mutations in the *cyp51A* gene, including TR34/L98H, TR53, and TR46/Y121F/T289A resistance mechanisms. Dudakova et al (3) have revealed differences between A.

and identical sensitivities against ITZ, VRZ, and PSZ, the isoenzymes showed differential tolerance of fluconazole, Denardi et al (10) study, evaluated the *fumigatus* Cyp51A and Cyp51B; despite identical substrate preferences which was significantly increased for Cyp51A compared to that of Cyp51B (9). susceptibility profile of *A. fumigatus* and *A. flavus*, isolated from patients with different forms of aspergillosis and from the environment in southern Brazil, against azoles, amphotericin B (AMB), and echinocandins. The resistance of *A. fumigatus* to the azole drugs might be due to the cross-resistance to the agricultural triazoles. Resistance rates vary widely across medical centers around the world, with some studies showing high resistance rates (11) and others with rates even lower than 1% (12). As an alternative to the use of azoles, lipid formulations of AMB and echinocandins are also being used nowadays in the treatment of aspergillosis (13). Owing to the widespread use of azoles in the treatment of aspergillosis and the potential consequence of acquiring azole resistance.

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